

SOCIO-DEMOGRAPHIC ASPECTS OF LABOR MIGRATION

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Annotation. This article examines the problems of labor migration and its socio-demographic costs. In modern conditions, the nature of migration is changing, new forms of territorial and labor migration and population movements are emerging.

Key words: demographic situation, demographic potential, labor migration, migration situation, migration policy, labor export.

The demographic situation is a complex socio-economic process that characterizes the dynamics of the country's population, its main sources, natural reproduction and family structure of the population, migration of the population, its location and urbanization, national and social composition of the population, labor resources and employment, etc.

The demographic situation at the turn of the 20th and 21st centuries acquired qualitatively new features. In many economically highly developed countries, the reproductive function of society has decreased to a point. Does not ensure the reproduction of the population and the birth rate has fallen below the threshold of simple generation replacement, and in this case we can already talk about a demographic crisis. At the same time, at one time in history the world population growth rate in absolute numbers was not high. By the end of the twentieth century, the planet's population exceeded 6 billion people. and this growth is projected to continue. The current very high rate of world population growth is determined to a

decisive extent by the rate of its increase in developing countries, where about 80% of the world's population lived by the end of the twentieth century. Against this background, in developed countries in the last decades of the twentieth century, the problem of labor shortage arose, caused primarily by a drop in the birth rate and increasing structural imbalances in the labor market. In the conditions of replenishment of the need for labor is carried out by attracting it from abroad. As a result, more than 150 million people (or approximately 2.5% of the total population of the planet) currently live in countries other than those where they were born.

Demographic problems are characteristic of almost all countries of the modern world. Taking this into account, the First President of the Republic of Uzbekistan I.A. Karimov identified as one of the priorities of market reforms at their current stage “the implementation of a strong social policy, taking into account the demographic and other specific national characteristics of the population.¹”

While in a number of countries the population has decreased significantly during the transition to market relations, in Uzbekistan it continues to grow.

Uzbekistan is one of the most labor-rich CIS countries.

Since the beginning of the twentieth century, the population of Uzbekistan has grown almost seven times and as of January 1, 2024 it amounted to more than 36.8 million people². According to a number of forecasts, fairly high rates of population growth will remain in Uzbekistan until the middle of the 21st century, although, according to UN forecasts, in the next 20-25 years they will still decrease significantly³, which was already observed in the last 20 years of the 20th century. Along with this, we believe that already now, and even more so in the near future, the demographic situation in the country will change in the direction that is typical

¹ Karimov I.A. Main directions for further deepening democratic reforms and forming the foundations of civil society in Uzbekistan. T. Uzbekistan, 2002. - p. 64.

² Data from the Stat Agency of the Republic of Uzbekistan. T; 2024

³ New UN report. 2024

for developed countries. Accordingly, the expansion of migration processes, including labor migration, outside the republic is expected.

The formation of a market economy has a great impact on migration processes in all countries including Uzbekistan. In the new economic conditions, the nature of migration changes significantly, new forms of territorial and labor migration and population movements appear. However, the migration situation in Uzbekistan at the beginning of the 21st century remains generally stable, despite the fact that radical changes in the socio-economic system of society have qualitatively changed it, since the basic migration flows, which had an internal union character, have moved into the category of external ones. And although in the process of the collapse of the former union and the formation of an independent state in Uzbekistan, certain difficulties arose in this area, subsequently external migration flows stabilized as well as the socio-economic situation in the country itself. The stabilization of external migration processes also affected internal migration. Moreover, in recent years, all major migration flows in the country have been decreasing in volume. Nevertheless, in Uzbekistan, 200-250 thousand people change their place of permanent residence every year, including more than 100 thousand people of the titular population (in Uzbekistan these are Uzbeks, Karakalpaks).

Since Uzbekistan, according to the definition of some economists, belongs to the so-called “labor surplus” states, the export of labor as an economic resource can become one of the important components that help implement the strategy of creating an effective economy. In addition to the undoubted benefit from additional foreign exchange earnings, due to labor migration, the problem of employment and unemployment is solved to a certain extent, and savings are also realized due to the reduction of costs for training and retraining of personnel, and advanced training of workers. The efficiency of labor exports is several times higher than the efficiency of goods exports.

It is interesting to emphasize that since the signing of a bilateral agreement between Uzbekistan and South Korea in 2007, the number of legal Uzbek migrants arriving in South Korea has been growing. From 10,000 migrants in 2005, the number of Uzbek migrants in South Korea increased fivefold, reaching 50,000 in 2015. This number has been growing since the signing of a memorandum in 2015/2016 on an agreement to stimulate economic cooperation between the two countries. Considering the wide demand of the state to support labor migrants abroad, the government of Uzbekistan is taking measures to cooperate with countries that receive labor migrants from Uzbekistan. Along with large migration projects in recent years, an agreement “On the organized recruitment and attraction of citizens of the Republic of Uzbekistan for temporary labor activities in Russia”⁴ was recently adopted. This agreement was approved by Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated June 19, 2017 No. PP -3069 “On approval of international treaties.”

To create working conditions in the Russian Federation, a comprehensive exam is carried out to identify knowledge of the Russian language, history, and the fundamentals of Russian legislation. A detailed “road map” for the implementation of systematic work in the field of labor migration in cooperation with the Russian Federation was approved. To date, the agency has concluded agreements with the Russian Federation, European countries, Japan and South Korea, which is a big step in the development of migration legislation based on the experience of this country.

Uzbekistan needs to use its high demographic potential much more intensively in the interests of stable economic growth and sustainable social development.

Therefore, the Government of the Republic of Uzbekistan has outlined measures to fulfill tasks in the field of migration policy of the country. The primary ones are the regulation of migration flows, overcoming the negative consequences

⁴ Agreement on the organized recruitment and attraction of citizens of the Republic of Uzbekistan to carry out temporary labor activities on the territory of the Russian Federation. M: 04/05/2017 <http://ru.sputniknews-uz.com/migration/20170921/6359969/Skolko-stoit-migraciya-v-Rossiyu.html>.

of spontaneously developing processes in this area, and creating conditions for the unhindered implementation of the rights of migrants. The practical implementation of constitutional and legislative norms ensuring the rights of Uzbek citizens to work abroad is facilitated by the concluded international agreements of Uzbekistan with Germany, South Korea, Russia and a number of other countries.

In the course of our research, special attention was paid to changes in gender characteristics of labor migration. Currently, almost 50% of informal labor migrants are women. Analysis shows that their number tends to increase. This situation is largely due to structural changes in the global economy. The development of the “household services economy”, “hotel industry”, as well as the growing need for care services for the elderly, sick and children, increases the demand for female labor. In these areas, women mainly occupy jobs that do not require high qualifications. In our opinion, the increase in the share of women in migration flows indicates a tendency towards the marginalization of a fairly large group of migrants in the global labor market. Consequently, gender issues of labor migration remain relevant. Among Uzbek labor migrants working in foreign countries, women make up almost 30.0%. Research results indicate that the majority of them are employed in jobs that do not require high qualifications. In many cases, the rights of women leaving the republic “illegally” are violated, and in some cases they are subjected to violence. In this regard, solving problems of protecting the rights of female labor migrants should be among the priorities of national and international institutions dealing with labor migration issues.

Each stage of the country’s socio-economic development poses certain problems in the formation and use of labor potential, which require appropriate developments in relation to specific conditions, as a prerequisite for managing ongoing processes in the interests of the development of the entire society. Labor migration is beneficial for participants in this process. So migrant;

- has financial resources to develop his own business;

- independently financially supports the family;
- “self-establishes itself” as a professional in his field or independently retrains in one or another specialty that can actually be in demand in the labor market, both abroad and in his own country.

Thus, spontaneous and informal external labor migration is fraught with such negative consequences as:

- an increase in the number of divorces as a result of prolonged separation between spouses;
- the negative impact of the long absence of one of the parents or both, who left for work, on raising children;
- migrants receiving labor injuries due to the lack of a labor protection system;
- low security at retirement age due to unaccounted work experience while staying abroad as a labor migrant;
- importation and spread of diseases.

The Migration Service of the Republic of Uzbekistan has granted licenses to several dozen organizations involved in the registration of employment of Uzbek citizens abroad. The introduction of the system made it possible to stop unscrupulous activities on the part of a number of companies and agencies. At the same time, many issues, including those related to the return of migrants, require further refinement and detail.

Considering that in recent years the proportion of women participating in external labor migration has been increasing, it is advisable to take measures to prevent their leaving the country by creating training centers for their training and advanced training. Increasing the level of knowledge and qualifications of women is an important factor in the socialization of the younger generation, as well as the formation and development of human capital. Because knowledge allows you to take advantage of the opportunities available in society, qualifications and skills ensure

social progress and economic growth. Thus, labor migration is an area in which the need for clear regulation and policy is particularly obvious. Therefore, a human rights approach to ensuring the protection of migrants and regulating migration processes is fundamentally important. This includes improving human rights legislation, recognizing international humane labor laws and respecting ethnic diversity. Such measures are a guarantee of democracy, peace and social stability.

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